

TECHNOLOGY OF ANIMATED TEACHING OF LABORATORY
SCHOOLS ON "CORROSION OF METALS" IN CHEMISTRY IN GENERAL
SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *This article discusses the issue of animation-based teaching of laboratory classes on "metal corrosion" in chemistry in secondary schools.*

Keywords: *general secondary school, chemistry, corrosion of metals, laboratory classes, teaching on the basis of animation, air, water, acid, alkali, solutions of salts, cathode, anode, visual aids, videos.*

At present, chemistry and chemical production play a very important role in the national economy. It made it possible to synthesize products that did not exist in nature, to use them to create a variety of machines and tools, to build residential buildings, and to produce consumer goods. Only raw materials, ore, coal, oil and others are extracted from nature.

Most metals are corroded by solutions of air, water, acids, alkalis, and salts. This phenomenon is called corrosion. The word corrosion comes from the Latin "corrodere" - meaning decay. Corrosion is of two types in terms of its physicochemical properties: chemical and electrochemical corrosion. Large quantities of basic chemical products - acids, alkalis, salts - are produced. The possibilities of chemistry are endless.

What type of corrosion occurs in metals depends on the environment around the metal. Chemical corrosion occurs when metals are exposed to dry gases (oxygen, sulfide anhydride, hydrogen sulfide, halogens, carbon dioxide, etc.), non-electrolyte liquids. This is especially common under high temperature conditions, so such decay is also called gas corrosion of metals. Gas corrosion is particularly damaging to metallurgy. To protect iron and steel products from gas corrosion, their surface is coated with aluminum.

Corrosion under the influence of liquid fuels is a chemical corrosion. The main components of liquid fuels do not corrode metals, but corrosion occurs as a result of exposure of metals to sulfur, hydrogen sulfide and organic sulfur in petroleum

and surkov oils. This effect is observed only in the absence of water. In water, it undergoes electrochemical corrosion.

Several measures are taken to protect metals from corrosion:

- a) coating the metal surface with other metals;
- b) coating the metal surface with non-metallic substances;
- d) introduction of various additives to metals;
- e) coating the metal surface with chemical compounds.

One method of coating a metal surface with other metals is anode coating. The standard electrode potential of the metal used for this purpose should have a negative value than that of the metal to be protected from corrosion along with the activity of the metals. For example, zinc plating of iron (anode plating) is of great benefit, because the iron object does not decompose until all the zinc covering its surface is finished.

When iron is coated with tin, a cathode coating is obtained because the coating metal coating is more original than the metal. If any part of the cathode coating moves, the protected metal, i.e. iron, will corrode very quickly.

Coating the surface of metals with varnish, paint, rubber, surkov oils (solid, technical Vaseline), enameling and so on protect metals from corrosion.

By adding 0.2-0.5% copper to ordinary steel, the corrosion resistance of steel can be increased by 1.5-2 times. Stainless steel contains up to 12% chromium, which is the passive state of chromium, giving the steel strength. When nickel and molybdenum are added to steel, its corrosion resistance is further increased. Such steels are called alloy steels.

Coating the metal surface with chemical compounds. By performing special chemical operations, the metal surface can be covered with a curtain of corrosion-resistant compounds. Such curtains are called oxide, phosphate, chromatic and other curtains. The process of forming a corrosion-resistant oxide film on a metal surface is called oxidation.

There are three ways to oxidize a metal piece:

- 1) the surface of a metal product is oxidized with organic matter at high temperatures (darkened, greened, etc.);
- 2) the metal product (such as MnO_2 ; $NaNO_3$; $K_2Cr_2O_7$) is heated to the boiling point of the liquid in a concentrated alkaline solution in the presence of oxidizing agents;
- 3) A metal object is electrolyzed by placing it in an electrolyte solution at the anode pole, a process called anodizing.

Corrosion activators and inhibitors. The rate of corrosion is greatly affected by the concentration of ions in solution, ie N^+ and ON^- ions, in solution - N. As the

concentration of N^+ ions increases, corrosion increases, and an increase in the concentration of OH^- ions reduces the corrosion of iron. However, the corrosion of metals (Zn, Al, Pb) whose hydroxides have amphoteric properties accelerates when the concentration of OH^- ions increases.

Execution of work

1. Required equipment: Glass tube, test tubes, cups,
2. Required reagents: 1.0 n of hydrochloric acid. solution, zinc plate, copper sulfate solution, zinc particle, aluminum particle, mercury (II) nitrate solution, copper chloride solution, red ore salt.

1-Experiment. The effect of galvanic couple formation on the melting process of a metal in acid.

1.0 n of hydrochloric acid in a glass tube bent at an angle. pour the solution and pour a narrow zinc plate on one of his elbows. Write the reaction equation.

Corrosion can be observed by releasing hydrogen bubbles. On the second elbow of the nay, pour copper wire into the same solution, so as not to touch the zinc plate. Make sure that no hydrogen is released on the copper surface. Insert more of the copper wire into the liquid until it is connected to the zinc. Hydrogen bubbles then form on the copper surface. Explain the processes that take place in this galvanic pair. Explain the cathode and anode in this

Thus, the teaching of laboratory classes in chemistry in vocational schools on the basis of animated lessons (on the example of laboratory work on "Metal corrosion" the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The use of interactive methods of advanced pedagogical technology facilitates the acquisition of knowledge by students, increases their activity in the classroom.
2. The use of modern information technologies in teaching facilitates the acquisition of scientific knowledge by students, plays an important role in creating a clear idea of the structure and principle of operation of equipment, the course of processes.
3. Micro-group teaching of chemistry in vocational schools is an effective method.
4. Focusing more on visual aids, animations, videos, and data sheets when creating lesson plans facilitates teaching and builds students' knowledge, skills, and abilities on the topic.

LITERATURE:

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